

Graduate Tracer Study of the Senior High School of St. Paul University Surigao, Philippines 2021-2022

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Abstract

This study traces the post-graduation trajectories of the 2021-2022 Senior High School graduates of St. Paul University Surigao (SPUS), evaluating the extent to which they embody the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes and Core Values, the significance of the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) acquired during their Senior High School (SHS) education, and the relevance of the SHS curriculum to their current endeavors. Utilizing a quantitative-descriptive design, data were collected via a survey from 185 graduates, selected through random sampling. The results indicate that the graduates find the SHS curriculum significantly relevant and beneficial in their higher education, work and business. The study highlights high levels of attainment in adaptability, self-direction, and media literacy, pointing to the curriculum's effectiveness in equipping students with necessary competencies. However, it also reveals areas needing enhancement, such as higher-order thinking skills. These findings provide valuable insights for SPUS to further refine its SHS programs to better prepare students for future challenges. The study underscores the importance of continuous curriculum evaluation and improvement in maintaining educational relevance and effectiveness.

Keywords: Graduate tracer study; Paulinian life performance outcomes; Senior high school curriculum; Essential learning competencies; Educational effectiveness

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Introduction

Tracer studies serve as indispensable tools for educational institutions, offering valuable insights into the effectiveness and relevance of their programs within the broader context of evolving academic and professional landscapes [1]. There is a need for educational institutions to continually evaluate and refine their programs to ensure they remain effective and relevant in a constantly evolving academic and professional environment. Without ongoing assessment, institutions risk delivering educational experiences that may not adequately prepare students for the demands of the workforce or further academic pursuits. Tracer studies provide a means to systematically track the outcomes of graduates, allowing institutions to gain valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of their programs and to identify areas for improvement.

A study conducted by Manchishi [2] tracking the experiences of alumni from the University of Zambia's Postgraduate Distance Education program, which was part of the UNZA-ZOU collaboration. The cohort enrolled in 2014 and graduated in 2016. The research revealed that some participants attained senior positions following their training, while others remained in their existing roles. Overall, participants expressed positive views about the programs, although a few raised concerns regarding research supervision and the quality of instructional materials.

As a result, the study recommended further investigation into employers' perspectives through a mini-study.

In the Philippines, a study conducted by Dialde [3] shows that there is a little research on the Senior High School graduates. It revealed that only 65.4% of respondents who are college students have courses that correspond to their SHS strands. This discrepancy suggests a potential mismatch between the skills and knowledge acquired during SHS and the requirements of tertiary education. Such findings underscore the necessity for further investigation into the effectiveness of SHS programs in adequately preparing students for their chosen academic pathways.

One observation at St. Paul University Surigao (SPUS) that could prompt the conduct of the Graduate Tracer Study of Senior High School (SHS) for the academic years 2021-2022 is the lack of comprehensive data on the post-graduation trajectories of SHS graduates. While SPUS may have anecdotal information about where graduates go after completing their SHS education, there might be a gap in understanding the specific pathways they pursue, such as higher education, employment, or entrepreneurship. Additionally, there could be uncertainty regarding how well the SHS curriculum aligns with the needs of students as they transition to further education or the workforce. Therefore, conducting a tracer study would help bridge this research gap by systematically tracking the experiences of SHS graduates from SPUS, providing valuable insights into their educational and career outcomes, and

informing future curriculum enhancements or support programs. This study aimed to trace the extent of attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values, significance of the most essential learning competencies in SHS and the relevance of the SHS curriculum (performance standards) to current endeavor. By tracing the relevance of the SHS curriculum, particularly its performance standards, to the current endeavors of graduates, this research contributes valuable insights into the effectiveness of the educational programs offered at SPUS. Ultimately, the findings of this study serve as a foundation for ongoing efforts to enhance the educational experiences and outcomes of SHS students, ensuring they are adequately prepared to thrive in their future endeavors and embody the values of the Paulinian community.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to trace the extent of attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values, significance of the most essential learning competencies in SHS and the relevance of the SHS curriculum (performance standards) to current endeavor. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Enrolled in higher education;
 - 1.2 Course;
 - 1.3 Currently employed;
 - 1.4 Employment status;
 - 1.5 Year of employment;
 - 1.6 Currently engaged in business; and
 - 1.7 Reasons not engaged in business?
2. What are the frequent reasons of the respondents to continue enrolling in St. Paul University Surigao and/or discontinue from it?
3. What is the extent of attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values of the respondents?
4. What is the extent of significance of the Most Essential Learning Competencies in SHS to Current Endeavor of the respondents?
5. What is the extent of relevance of the SHS curriculum (Performance Standards) to Current Endeavor of the respondents?
6. Is there a significant difference on the extent of attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values of the graduates when grouped according to their chosen course?
7. Based from the results, what recommendations may be proposed?

Hypothesis

At 0.05 level of significance, there is no significant difference on the extent of attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values of the graduates when grouped according to their chosen course.

Methodology

In this study, the researchers used a quantitative-descriptive design that used a survey method to gather the data with respect for the graduates' profile, attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values, significance of the most essential learning competencies in SHS and the relevance of the SHS curriculum (performance standards) to current endeavor. The participants involved in this research study were the 2022 graduates of the Senior High School. Out of 343 total graduates of the Senior High school SY 2021-2022 at St. Paul University Surigao, the researchers were able to select 185 respondents using Slovin's formula. The floating of questionnaire via Google Forms was conducted through a simple random sampling. The names of the graduates were acquired from the SHS Assistant Principals office. Nevertheless, the study did not require a fixed study site as the participants that would be involved are not all expected to be on the premises of or employed in Saint Paul University Surigao. It was considered that other participants may have been in other places, organizations, agencies, or anywhere.

Utilizing the Senior High school Graduates Tracer Study (GTS) instrument provided by the Basic Education research coordinator's office, the researcher employed the given survey questionnaire. The adopted survey questionnaire includes four significant parts: demographic profile, attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values, significance of the Most Essential Learning Competencies in SHS and the relevance of the SHS curriculum (performance standards) to current endeavor.

In achieving the primal objective of having the most reliable and appropriate results and findings, the researchers employed the following statistical tools to treat and analyze the data:

Frequency Count and Percentage Computation. These were used to determine the distribution in the demographic profile of the respondents, frequent reasons for employment and/or business, and frequent reasons to continue enrolling in St. Paul University Surigao or discontinue from it.

Mean and Standard Deviation. These were used to determine the extent of attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values, significance of the most essential learning competencies in SHS and the relevance of the SHS curriculum (performance standards) to current endeavor.

Analysis of Variance. These were used to determine the significant difference on the level of attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values of the graduates when grouped according to their chosen course.

Results and Discussions

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of enrolled in higher education, course, currently employed, employment status, year of employment, currently engaged in business, and reasons not engaged in business.

Table 1: Profile of the Respondents.

Profile	f (185)	%
Enrolled in Higher Education		
Yes	179	97
No	6	3
Course		
AB Political Science	12	7
BS Accountancy	14	8
BS Agriculture	7	4
BS Business Administration	13	7
BS Criminology	13	7
BS Hospitality Management	17	9
BS Management Accounting	7	4
BS in Nursing	28	15
BS in Tourism Management	7	4
Bachelor of Sports Science	6	3
BS Financial Management	9	5
BS Marketing Management	7	4
BS Civil Engineering	13	7
BS Architecture	7	4
Education	11	6
BS Computer Engineering	7	4
BS Biology	7	4
Currently Employed		
Yes	34	18
No	151	82
Employment Status		
Contractual	6	3
Regular/Permanent	5	3
Did not look for a job	17	9
No job opportunity	6	3
Not Applicable	151	82
Year of Employment		
2022	5	3
2023	17	9
2024	12	7
Not Applicable	151	82
Currently Engaged in Business		
Yes (Online Selling/Re-selling)	3	2
No	182	98
Reasons Not Engaged in Business		
Plan to go to college	131	71
Lack of Capital	25	14
Undecided on what business to put up	19	10
Health Related Reason	6	3
Plans to get Employed	1	1
Not Applicable	3	2

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents. In total, 185 students were included in the study. A significant majority, 97% (179

respondents), are currently enrolled in higher education, with only 3% (6 respondents) not pursuing higher education. The respondents are enrolled in various courses with the following distribution: AB Political Science has 12 respondents, making up 7% of the total. BS Accountancy has 14 respondents, which is 8%. BS Agriculture has 7 respondents, accounting for 4%. BS Business Administration and BS Criminology each have 13 respondents, both constituting 7%. BS Hospitality Management has 17 respondents, representing 9%. BS Management Accounting, BS in Tourism Management, BS Marketing Management, BS Architecture, BS Computer Engineering, and BS Biology each have 7 respondents, making up 4% each. BS in Nursing has the highest number of respondents at 28, accounting for 15%. Bachelor of Sports Science has 6 respondents, which is 3%. BS Financial Management has 9 respondents, representing 5%. BS Civil Engineering has 13 respondents, making up 7%. Finally, the Education course has 11 respondents, accounting for 6% of the total.

In terms of employment, 18% (34 respondents) are currently employed, while 82% (151 respondents) are not employed. Among the employed respondents, 3% are on contractual terms, another 3% have regular or permanent positions, 9% did not look for a job, and 3% cited no job opportunities. The majority, 82%, marked employment status as not applicable. Regarding the year of employment, 3% started in 2022, 9% in 2023, and 7% in 2024, with 82% indicating the year as not applicable.

When it comes to business engagement, only 2% (3 respondents) are involved in online selling or re-selling, while 98% (182 respondents) are not engaged in business. The reasons for not engaging in business include plans to go to college (71%), lack of capital (14%), indecision about what business to start (10%), health-related reasons (3%), and plans to get employed (1%), with 2% citing other reasons.

Table 2: Reasons to Continue/Discontinue Enrolling in St. Paul University Surigao.

Reasons	f (N=185)	%
For Choosing SPUS		
Teacher Factor	14	8
School Factor	26	14
Student Factor	26	14
Not Applicable	66	36
For Not Choosing SPUS		
Teacher Factor	7	4
School Factor	7	4
Student Factor	49	27
Financial Considerations	34	18
Try Other University	22	12
Not Applicable	119	64

Table 2 shows the reasons to continue/discontinue enrolling in St. Paul University Surigao in terms of choosing and not choosing SPUS. As to choosing SPUS, 66(36%) participants belong to not applicable, then school factor together with student factor with 26(14%), and teacher factor with 14(8%). In terms of not choosing

SPUS, 199(64%) are not applicable; 49(27%) are student factor; 34(18%) are financial considerations; 22(12%) are trying other university; and 7(4%) are teacher factor and school.

According to Cabrigas [4], as one participates in flexible learning classes, instructors and students alike feel that students possess high levels of academic integrity, particularly in terms of honesty, trust, respect, accountability, fairness, and courage. Therefore, it can be concluded that St. Paul University Surigao's Paulinian Remote Flexible Learning scheme is successful in fostering high-quality education while maintaining the inculcation of Paulinian core values in the context of the new normal and bolstering the foundational values and markers of academic integrity. Gaddi [5], stated that enrolling in St. Paul University Surigao has several advantages. Through innovative programs like Block Scheduling and Remote Flexible Learning, the university has successfully promoted academic integrity, enhanced employability through

high-quality instruction and student support services, and provided effective learning experiences.

Additionally, Gaddi [6] said that the programs at St. Paul University Surigao were highly successful in terms of high-quality instruction, student involvement in activities, the learning environment, and student support services. It demonstrated that the institution recognized and used indicators to improve the facilitation of the graduates' learning experience, which is both concretely and holistically responsive. According to the report, the school should consistently prioritize teacher professional development, dynamic program evaluation, and effective school leadership-all of which are essential for implementing academic programs successfully.

Extent of attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values, significance of the most essential learning competencies in SHS and the relevance of the SHS curriculum (performance standards) to current endeavor.

Table 3: Attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values.

INDICATORS	M	SD	VI	QD
Mindful, Self-Directed Learners and Role Models/ Christ-Centeredness (Conscious)				
Learn independently and act as role model in loving and following Jesus Christ	3.66	0.681	A	TVME
Observe Catholic practices, such as regular attendance at Mass, Confession, devotion to the Holy Rosary, among others.	3.81	0.468	A	TVME
Respect himself/herself by being decent and modest in his/her dressing, manners, and speech both in public and private places.	3.65	0.541	A	TVME
Manage time and energy to allow for regular periods of quiet reflection and prayer, renewal and directions setting.	3.84	0.37	A	TVME
Average:	3.72	0.52	A	TVME
Creative, Resourceful Explorers and Problem Solvers/ Charism (Creative)				
Work hard to develop God-given talents for the love of God and in the service of church, family and community.	3.81	0.393	A	TVME
Open to new inputs, suggestions and know how to adjust in different situations.	3.77	0.42	A	TVME
Accomplish task with determination, have good time management and have self-discipline.	3.74	0.44	A	TVME
Share talents and resources to anyone especially those in need	3.68	0.533	A	TVME
Inspire others to do their very best, using their highest potential in any performance	3.71	0.52	A	TVME
Average:	3.74	0.46	A	TVME
Caring, Committed Advocates for Peace and Universal Well-Being/Charity (Compassion)				
Show compassion especially to the needy.	3.84	0.365	A	TVME
Share time, resources and energy to others willingly.	3.78	0.416	A	TVME
Accept defeat and celebrate others' success.	3.81	0.393	A	TVME
Care for environment and utilize resources wisely and economically.	3.81	0.397	A	TVME

Behave well everywhere and wait patiently for his/her turn.	3.81	0.397	A	TVME
Average:	3.81	0.39	A	TVME
Credible, Responsive Communicators and Team Players/Community (Collaboration)				
Demonstrate habits that promote success of the community and the skills needed to participate in democratic process.	3.81	0.397	A	TVME
Demonstrate positive interpersonal relationships and sensitivity to the feelings of others.	3.75	0.437	A	TVME
Communicate and work well with others to resolve conflicts fairly	3.81	0.397	A	TVME
Volunteer and offer assistance and support whenever needed.	3.71	0.456	A	TVME
Exert effort to promote unity and cooperation.	3.74	0.44	A	TVME
Average:	3.76	0.43	A	TVME
Conscientious, Adept Performers and Achievers/Commission (Competence)				
Demonstrate initiatives to advance skills and seek expert's opinion to look for credible facts and evidences.	3.75	0.437	A	TVME
Continue doing work despite difficult situations.	3.81	0.393	A	TVME
Stay focused on completing quality projects and on task given	3.81	0.397	A	TVME
Use logical reasoning in problem-solving and good interpersonal skills to influence others	3.71	0.453	A	TVME
Take mistakes as opportunities for learning, growth and development.	3.84	0.365	A	TVME
Average:	3.78	0.41	A	TVME
General Average:	3.76	0.44	A	TVME

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Code	Qualitative Description	Code
4	3.25-4.00	Always	A	To a Very High/Much Extent	TVME
3	2.50-3.24	Ofentimes	O	To Some Extent	TSE
2	1.75-2.49	Sometimes	S	To Little Extent	TLE
1	1.00-1.74	Rarely	R	To No Extent At All	TNE

Table 3 shows the Attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values. In terms of *Mindful, Self-Directed Learners and Role Models Christ-Centeredness (Conscious)*, the indicator, *Manage time and energy to allow for regular periods of quiet reflection and prayer, renewal and directions setting* got the highest mean (M=3.84, SD=0.370), which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This means that the participants make sure they plan their time and energy well to have regular moments for quiet thinking, prayer, and recharging themselves. This helps them stay connected spiritually and also gives them time to think about their goals and plans for the future. However the indicator *Respect himself/herself by being decent and modest in his/her dressing, manners, and speech both in public and private places* got the lowest mean (M=3.65, SD=0.541), which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This means that the participants maintains self-respect by portraying modesty and decency in their choice of clothing, conduct, and communication, regardless of

whether they are in public or private spaces. By adhering to these principles, individuals not only preserve their own dignity but also contribute to fostering a respectful and harmonious social environment. Additionally, according to Joudeh [7] dress is not a mere choice an individual makes; rather, it metonymizes almost every aspect of one's identity. Through a critical analysis of Arab British novelists Willow Trees Don't Weep and Lyrics Alley, the paper accentuates the skillful employment of dress in these novels and highlights its different implications. It also brings to light the strong relationship between the main characters and their choice of dress.

On average, the participants' Attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values in terms of *Mindful, Self-Directed Learners and Role Models Christ-Centeredness (Conscious)* (M=3.72 SD=0.52) is verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. In this study, participants show they can learn independently and express their commitment to Jesus Christ. They also follow Catholic practices like going to Mass and Confession,

as well as respecting themselves by dressing modestly and behaving respectfully. Additionally, they set aside time for reflection, prayer, and self-renewal.

In terms of *Creative, Resourceful Explorers and Problem Solvers Charism (Creative)*, the indicator *Work hard to develop God-given talents for the love of God and in the service of church, family and community* got the highest mean ($M=3.81$, $SD=0.393$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. It implies that the majority of respondents value the cultivation of their talents in a manner that aligns with their faith and commitment to serving others within their various area of influence, including the church, family, and community. This value likely reflects the emphasis on personal growth, faith-based service, and community engagement within the Paulinian spirit.

Hence, the indicator *Share talents and resources to anyone especially those in need* got the lowest mean ($M=3.68$, $SD=0.533$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This could imply that while participants recognize the importance of sharing talents and resources with those in need, there may be varying degrees of agreement or interpretation regarding the extent or methods of implementing this value. It could also reflect different perspectives on the practicality or feasibility of sharing resources, or varying levels of personal engagement with this aspect of service within the Paulinian community. According to the research of Saikkonen and Kaarakainen [8], research on 21st-century skills reveals digital skills evolve sequentially, building on information skills, making them crucial for teachers to pass on to future generations. Overall, while it may not have received the highest mean, this indicator still demonstrates a commitment to service and unselfishness among participants, although with some variation in perceptions or attitudes.

On average, the participants' Attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values in terms of *Creative, Resourceful Explorers and Problem Solvers Charism (Creative)*, ($M=3.74$ $SD=0.46$) is verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. The average mean score indicates a consensus among participants, as it falls closer to the upper end of the rating scale. This suggests that the majority of respondents perceive the Paulinian Core Values positively and endorse their importance. Additionally, the relatively small range of 0.46 suggests a moderate level of variability in responses across the different indicators. This indicates that while there may be some variation in how strongly individuals endorse specific values, the overall trend is one of general agreement. This conclusion emphasizes the strength of the Paulinian Core Values within the community and highlights the shared commitment to these principles among participants in the study.

In terms of *Caring, Committed Advocates for Peace and Universal Well-Being Charity (Compassion)*, the indicator, *Show compassion especially to the needy* got the highest mean ($M=3.84$,

$SD=0.365$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. Participants in this activity display kindness and generosity by helping others in need, encouraging personal growth, and fostering a sense of community. These values are rooted in compassion and empathy, which promote good deeds and awareness of well-being, leaving a lasting legacy of faith. According to a study by Jiayu [9], various factors affect whether students demonstrate compassion towards those in need. Urbanization has changed the traditional practices of hosting and sponsoring needy students, which has impacted their support systems.

However, the indicator, *A Share time, resources and energy to others willingly* got the lowest mean ($M=3.78$, $SD=0.416$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. Sharing can help others in various positive ways. But despite that, many people are not willing to do so because of the negative impacts they assume will happen once this action is taken. According to Babcock [10], a few of the reasons people are not willing to share is because they believe knowledge is power, people are insecure about the value of their knowledge, people don't trust each other, employees are afraid of negative consequences, and lastly people work for other people who don't tell what they know.

On average, *Caring, Committed Advocates for Peace and Universal Well-Being Charity (Compassion)* ($M=3.81$, $SD=0.39$) is verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This observation implies that the respondents in this study are open minded and kind hearted. Implying good actions in their day to day lives that aligns with the teachings of God, showcasing these deeds everywhere they go.

Among the five indicators in terms of *Credible, Responsive Communicators and Team Players Community (Collaboration)*, the item *Demonstrate habits that promote success of the community and the skills needed to participate in democratic process* and *Communicate and work well with others to resolve conflicts fairly* got the highest mean ($M=3.81$, $SD=0.397$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. It connotes that students have the habits to promote the success of the community as well as the skills to communicate and work well with others. A study published by Karasova and Nehyba [11], found that student-centered communication practices in the classroom were associated with increased prosocial behavior, behavioral engagement, and learning outcomes. Thus, most of the students have communication skills that affect their behavior with others. As well as have the value that promotes the success of the community.

On the other hand, the item *Volunteer and offer assistance and support whenever needed* got the lowest mean ($M=3.71$, $SD=0.456$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. It means that graduates offer assistance whenever possible. According to Gladstone [12], mutual support among students leads to mutual success, fosters a positive learning environment, and encourages

empathy and collaboration. Hence, with the students being readily available to provide assistance, they contribute to the success of the community.

On average, the attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values in terms of *Credible, Responsive Communicators and Team Players Community (Collaboration)*, verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent* (M=3.76, SD=0.43). It means that the graduates are meeting the expectations to actively contribute to the success and cohesion of the community. Most students demonstrated positive interpersonal relationships, communicated well with others, volunteered assistance, and provided promotion for unity. According to Davis [13], the values students embody determine their attitudes and motivations; they also help them grow, develop, and create the future they want to experience.

As shown in the table the attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values in terms of *Conscientious, Adept Performers and Achievers Commission (Competence)* indicator 5, *Take mistakes as opportunities for learning, growth and development* got the highest mean (M=3.84, SD=0.365), which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This means that most graduates learn from their own mistakes and make improvements. According to Colea [14], mistakes are an important source of development, especially when managed effectively. The study suggests that mistakes can help students learn by encouraging them to explore, analyze, and identify ways to deal with errors.

However, the indicator, *Use logical reasoning in problem-solving and good interpersonal skills to influence others* got the lowest mean (M=3.71, SD=0.453), which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This means that graduates employ logical thinking in solving problems and use interpersonal skills to effectively communicate and persuade others. According to a study by Ramganes and Reddy [15], it was indicated that higher logical reasoning skills are linked to better academic performance, with logical reasoning being a predictor of success. The findings of the study emphasize the importance of logical reasoning skills in shaping students' academic performance, highlighting how these skills are essential

for understanding complex concepts, problem-solving, and achieving success in academic subjects.

On average, the attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values in terms of *Conscientious, Adept Performers and Achievers Commission (Competence)*, verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This signifies that graduates consistently apply these competencies in their higher education, work, or business endeavors. Conscientiousness and competence are critical predictors of success, with conscientious individuals excelling academically due to their organization and responsibility, and in the workplace for their reliability and efficiency. Competent graduates are well-prepared to tackle advanced studies,

professional challenges, and entrepreneurial ventures, demonstrating adaptability and informed decision-making. This consistent application of core values enhances personal and professional success, contributing positively to the broader community. Recent studies confirm that conscientiousness and competence are among the strongest predictors of performance in various life domains, highlighting the importance of these traits in achieving long-term success.

Furthermore, the attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values (M=3.76, SD=0.44) can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This implies that the graduates consistently demonstrate the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Core Values in their endeavor. According to Imperial [16], school core values significantly influence the desirable behaviors, beliefs, and attitudes of students, with both students and teachers strongly agreeing on this influence. While it is evident that students attaining to core values determine their behaviors, more research is needed to find out how they truly apply the values to themselves. Additional studies on the importance of the school's core values may provide better knowledge about the students' manners. In brief, the attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values is ranked according to the obtained average mean points or their effect on students. To wit: Rank 1: *Charity (Compassion)*, Rank 2: *Commission (Competence)*, Rank 3: *Community (Collaboration)*, Rank 4: *Charism (Creative)*, and Rank 5: *Christ-Centeredness (Conscious)*.

Table 4: Significance of the Most Essential Learning Competencies in SHS to Current Endeavor.

INDICATORS	M	SD	VI	QD
Learning and Innovation Skills				
Creativity and curiosity	3.72	0.451	A	TVME
Critical thinking, problem solving, and risk-taking	3.69	0.465	A	TVME
Adaptability, managing complexity and self-direction	3.82	0.388	A	TVME
Higher-order thinking and sound reasoning	3.63	0.485	A	TVME
Average:	3.72	0.45	A	TVME
Information, Media, and Technology Skills				
Visual and information literacies	3.62	0.486	A	TVME

Media literacy	3.62	0.486	A	TVME
Basic, scientific, economic, and technological literacies	3.59	0.493	A	TVME
Multicultural literacy and global awareness	3.56	0.497	A	TVME
Average:	3.6	0.49	A	TVME
Effective Communication Skills				
Teaming, collaboration and interpersonal skills	3.69	0.465	A	TVME
Personal, social, and civic responsibility	3.69	0.465	A	TVME
Interactive communication	3.69	0.463	A	TVME
Average:	3.69	0.46	A	TVME
Life and Career Skills				
Flexibility and adaptability	3.69	0.531	A	TVME
Initiative and self-direction	3.65	0.477	A	TVME
Social and cross-cultural skills	3.62	0.549	A	TVME
Productivity and accountability	3.62	0.606	A	TVME
Leadership and responsibility	3.7	0.516	A	TVME
Average:	3.66	0.54	A	TVME
General Average:	3.67	0.48	A	TVME

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Code	Qualitative Description	Code
4	3.25-4.00	Always	A	To a Very High/Much Extent	TVME
3	2.50-3.24	Ofentimes	O	To Some Extent	TSE
2	1.75-2.49	Sometimes	S	To Little Extent	TLE
1	1.00-1.74	Rarely	R	To No Extent At All	TNE

Table 4 shows that the Significance of the Most Essential Learning Competencies in SHS to Current Endeavor, in terms of Adaptability, *managing complexity*, and *self-direction* obtained the highest Mean of (M= 3.82), and with a Standard Deviation of (SD=.388). Which can be Verbally interpreted as *Always*, and Qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This means that the graduates effectively observed the Adaptability of managing complexity and self-direction. As a result, this data shows that the Most Essential Learning Competencies play a significant role in the Senior High School's Current Endeavors. In the study of Gabriel [17], the Most Essential Learning Competencies was constructed as a response of the department in addressing difficulties in learning competencies during these trying times, this memorandum clarifies the utility of the pertinent learning competencies. Additionally, the Education department will be able to concentrate instruction on the skills that students need to master thanks to the Most Essential Learning Competencies.

However, in the indicator, *Higher-order thinking and sound reasoning* obtained the lowest Mean of (M=3.63), with a Standard Deviation of (SD=.485). Which can be Verbally interpreted as *Always*, and Qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This means that the Most Essential Learning Competencies apply to the graduates Higher-order thinking and sound reasoning. As a result, the graduates from Senior High School enhanced their capability of Higher-order thinking skills and sound reasoning because of Most Essential Learning Competencies. This implies that Higher-order thinking skills go beyond basic observation of

facts and memorization. Moreover, many professional educators agree that higher-order thinking skills are important to consider when developing lesson plans, providing instruction and assessing student growth [18].

On average, the Significance of the Most Essential Learning Competencies in SHS to Current Endeavor in terms of *Learning and Innovation Skills*, with a Mean of (M= 3.72), and with a Standard Deviation of (SD= 0.45). Which can be Verbally interpreted as *Always*, and Qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This means that the students from Senior High School effectively observed the significance of Most Essential Learning Competencies to Current Endeavors. This finding implies that the students from Senior High School are affected positively by the help of the Most Essential Learning Competencies in Current Endeavors. In effect, the Most Essential Learning Competencies ensures that students must acquire the necessary competencies and skills that are essential for their future success. Furthermore, compromising the Most Essential Learning Competencies will also compromise the quality of Education. Therefore, Most Essential Learning Competencies assist students from Senior High School in designing and delivering effective learning experiences that align with the needs and goals of the curriculum.

In terms of *Information, Media, and Technology Skills*, that indicators 1 and 2: *Visual and information literacies*, and *Media literacy*, had the same highest mean (M = 3.62, SD=0.486), which is verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This implies that the visual, information

and media literacy are consistently significant to the graduates in their future endeavor. Media and information literacy (MIL) has become a social necessity owing to the massive development of modern media resources such as social media, digital channels, and electronic news sites, which together confront individuals with a vast amount of information, headlines, new technologies, and different opinions. Making the next generation aware of how to interact with different forms of media is crucial because they will convey the news and information they encounter and are often responsible for producing it [19].

On the other hand, in variable 4, *Multicultural literacy and global awareness* had the lowest mean ($M=3.56$, $SD=0.497$), which is still verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This means that the graduates find it significant in the Higher Education, Employment and Business. Since it is lowest, there are still few who didn't find it significant to their extent. According to Asten, in modern society, ethnic conflicts, intolerance, lack of understanding of the problems of people of other faiths, ignorance by many culture of other peoples, and inability to choose the correct form of behavior towards representatives prove necessity for special work to prepare students to communicate in a multicultural environment. Students are called to adequately and dynamically contact with the world around them, with themselves, with other people, and skilfully interact with the multicultural environment. It could be the problem of forming the readiness of graduates to communicate in a multicultural environment makes a certain contribution to the possibility of educating a young person focused on understanding, tolerance, acceptance, and respect for cultural diversity.

Meanwhile, the significance of the most essential learning competencies in shs to current endeavor in terms of *Information, Media, and Technology Skills* ($M =3.60$, $SD=0.49$), is verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This indicates that the use of information, media, and technology skills helps the graduates develop their learning competencies in their current endeavor. In today's digital landscape, where access to vast amounts of information is ubiquitous, the ability to effectively navigate, evaluate, and utilize this information is paramount. Information skills empower graduates to sift through the abundance of data, discerning credible sources and extracting relevant insights efficiently. Moreover, media literacy skills are essential in deciphering the multitude of media forms inundating society.

As shown from the variable *Effective Communication Skills*: the indicators *Teaming, collaboration and interpersonal skills* and *Personal, social, and civic responsibility* both got the highest mean ($M=3.69$, $SD=.465$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This means that the most essential learning competencies affect effective communication skills in terms of *Teaming, collaboration and interpersonal skills*, and SHS students' *Personal, social, and civic responsibility*. "Collaborative learning provides opportunities for students to engage in group discussions and be responsible for

the learning process being carried out. Furthermore, collaboration could not only be done between students but also with other parties as well as the surrounding environment, enumerating and explaining the different skills such as interpersonal skills, group management skills, inquiry skills, conflict skills, and presentation skills" [20].

However, the indicator *Interactive communication* got the same mean but got the lowest standard deviation ($M=3.69$, $SD=.463$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent* showing that most of the graduates from SHS have interactive communication but not the majority of the respondents. Although it may seem that there is always communication between the learner and the educator, communication does not always occur. The absence of time, shortage of resources, and lack of knowing how to exchange information can lead to ineffective communication. Once communication between the teacher and student is effective, both would benefit: the level of the student's enthusiasm would grow and the teacher would be a major influence on the child's learning. Effective communication helps people learn more easily, strengthens the relationship between the teacher and the learner, and creates a positive atmosphere in the learning environment [21]. On average, the variable *Effective Communication Skills* ($M=3.69$, $SD=0.46$), is verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This finding indicates that the most essential learning competencies have helped in making the respondents' communication skills effective. To be able to communicate with other people effectively, following the most essential learning competencies will aid students in having effective communication with other individuals.

As shown from the variable *Life and Career Skills*, the indicator *Leadership and responsibility* got the highest mean ($M = 3.70$, $SD = .516$), which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. Meaning, that the majority of the SHS students have the capability and skills to be leaders and are responsible in their academic endeavors. According to Schwegker and Dimitriou [22], leadership is the act of guiding, persuading, and monitoring people to carry out duties following predetermined instructions while bearing both material and spiritual responsibility for the work's accomplishment. Based on the results from the table, SHS students demonstrated their leadership and responsibility, encapsulating the true definition of such skills.

However, the indicator *Social and cross-cultural skills* got the lowest mean and standard deviation ($M=3.62$, $SD=.549$), which can still be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent* but is still considered the lowest among the five (5) variables. This means that the majority of SHS students do not entirely interact with other diverse groups and social situations. In doing so, Sulistyaningsih [23] suggest that students should interact effectively with others and work in diverse groups. Students need to be taught how to handle themselves and how to deal in such a setting, keeping an open mind and being

accepting of differing opinions and morals while taking into account the social, cultural, and ethnic backgrounds of others. On average, the participants' Life and Career Skills (M=3.66, SD=0.54) are interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This finding indicates that students from Senior High School greatly show their skills to the extent that they showcase their academic endeavors in terms of their lives and careers.

On general average, the factor, Significance of the Most Essential Learning Competencies in SHS to Current Endeavor (M=3.67, SD=0.48) is verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. Meaning, the findings indicate that the significance of the curriculum's MELC significantly aligns with the current endeavor, suggesting a strong correlation towards the students, specifically from the SHS, fostering skills that greatly affect every learner's academic initiatives.

Table 5: Relevance of the SHS Curriculum (Performance Standards) to Current Endeavor.

INDICATORS	M	SD	VI	QD
Core Subjects:				
Oral Communications	3.84	0.365	A	TVME
Komunikasyon at Pananaliksik sa Wika at Kulturang Filipino	3.41	0.709	A	TVME
Understanding Culture, Society & Politics	3.72	0.451	A	TVME
General Mathematics	3.45	0.706	A	TVME
Earth and Life Sciences	3.57	0.64	A	TVME
Personal Development	3.61	0.553	A	TVME
Introduction to Philosophy of the Human Person	3.5	0.669	A	TVME
Physical Education and Health	3.69	0.463	A	TVME
Reading and Writing	3.41	0.71	A	TVME
Pagbasa at Pagsuri ng Iba't - Ibang Teksto Tungo sa Pananaliksik	3.66	0.473	A	TVME
Media and Information Literacy	3.61	0.49	A	TVME
21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World	3.51	0.644	A	TVME
Physical Science	3.47	0.715	A	TVME
Statistics and Probability	3.48	0.66	A	TVME
Contemporary Philippine Arts from the Region	3.84	0.365	A	TVME
Average:	3.58	0.57	A	TVME
Contextualized Subjects:				
English for Academic and Professional Purposes	3.72	0.448	A	TVME
Research in Daily Life 1 and 2	3.69	0.529	A	TVME
Empowerment Technologies (E-Tech): ICT for Professional Tracks	3.32	0.73	A	TVME
Pagsulat sa Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Akademik)	3.28	0.728	A	TVME
Entrepreneurship	3.45	0.78	A	TVME
Inquiries, Investigation and Work Immersion	3.57	0.75	A	TVME
Average:	3.51	0.66	A	TVME
Specialized Subjects:				
Specialized Subjects for ABM	3.48	0.986	A	TVME
Specialized Subjects for HUMSS	3.74	0.606	A	TVME
Specialized Subjects for STEM	3.63	0.691	A	TVME
Specialized Subjects for TVL	2.98	0.948	O	TSE
Average:	3.46	0.81	A	TVME
General Average:	3.52	0.68	A	TVME

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Code	Qualitative Description	Code
4	3.25-4.00	<i>Always</i>	A	<i>To a Very High/Much Extent</i>	TVME
3	2.50-3.24	<i>Oftentimes</i>	O	<i>To Some Extent</i>	TSE
2	1.75-2.49	<i>Sometimes</i>	S	<i>To Little Extent</i>	TLE
1	1.00-1.74	<i>Rarely</i>	R	<i>To No Extent At All</i>	TNE

Table 5 presents the Relevance of the SHS Curriculum (Performance Standards) to Current Endeavor. As gleaned from the Table, the indicator, *Oral Communication and Contemporary Philippine Arts from the Region* got the highest mean ($M=3.84$, $SD=.365$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and quantitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This indicates a strong alignment between the SHS Curriculum's performance standards and the current endeavors, particularly in the areas of oral communication and the appreciation of contemporary Philippine arts from the region, suggesting a high level of proficiency and relevance in these aspects of education. Parupalli [24], oral communication skill is considered a crucial aspect of education, as it is seen as a vital tool for effective communication and interaction in various aspects of life, including personal, social, and professional settings. This emphasis is reflected in the curriculum, where subjects like oral communication are taught extensively to enhance students' ability to communicate effectively in English, which is the primary language of instruction in many schools. Additionally, the country's cultural and artistic heritage is rich and diverse, providing a strong foundation for students to develop their skills in various forms of artistic expression. According to the study of Fernandez [25], students excel in Philippine contemporary arts due to beneficial, challenging, and successful art-integrated performance tasks in ABM, HUMSS, and ADT strands, fostering creativity, critical thinking, cultural understanding and also it allows students to connect with and appreciate artistic expressions of their own culture and community.

However, the indicator, *Komunikasyon at Pananaliksik sa Wika at Kulturang Filipino and Reading and Writing* got the lowest mean ($M=3.41$, $SD=.709$ and $SD=.710$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and quantitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This means that despite being rated "Always", the lower mean scores suggest potential areas for improvement in communication and literacy skills within the Filipino language and culture, indicating a need for further attention and enhancement in these specific domains. Saavedra reveals that many elementary pupils struggle with poor writing [26].

On the average, the variable, *Core Subjects* ($M=3.58$, $SD=0.57$), is verbally interpreted as *Always* and quantitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This finding indicates that this SHS Curriculum's performance is consistently strong, with graduates demonstrating a high level of proficiency in core subjects to a Very High/Much Extent.

As gleaned from the Table, the indicator, *Contextualized Subjects: English for Academic and Professional Purposes* got the highest mean ($M=3.72$, $SD=.448$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This means that the subject English for Academic and Professional Purposes has great relevancy to the SHS curriculum to current endeavors. English for Academic and Professional Purposes allows learners to not only learn the English language for the sake of it, but because they need, or will need, to use English in their

professional or academic lives. This involves an attitude to learning and teaching that believes that it is possible and useful to specify what language and linguistic practices are required in a particular academic context and that it is worthwhile to focus teaching on this [27].

However, the indicator, *Contextualized Subjects: Pagsulat sa Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Akademik)* got the lowest mean ($M=3.28$, $SD=.728$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This means that the subject Pagsulat sa Filipino sa Piling Larangan (Akademik) has great relevancy to the SHS curriculum to current endeavors. It should take note of the importance of Filipino language. For it always plays second best to English, as some people don't think that there are any benefits when it comes to practicing, using, and being good at Filipino [28].

The average of the variable *Contextualized Subjects* ($M=3.51$, $SD=0.66$), is verbally interpreted as *Always* and quantitatively described as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This indicates that the use of contextualized subjects for the SHS Curriculum's performance standard has great relevancy. The implementation of these subjects greatly augments the flourishing knowledge of students, enabling learners to face current endeavors with efficiency.

As gleaned from the table, the indicator, *Specialized Subjects: Specialized Subjects for HUMSS* got the highest mean approximately at ($M=3.74$, $SD=0.606$) which can be verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively describe as *To a Very High/Much Extent*. This means that the Specialized Subjects in Humanities and Social Science Student (HUMSS) has great relevancy to the SHS curriculum to current students endeavors. The implementation of specialized subjects for the HUMSS strand further provides students with knowledge and skills into the investigation and inquiry of human situations by studying its behavior and social changes using empirical, analytical, and critical method techniques. It further immerses students to critical thinking and understanding skills [29].

However, the indicator, *Specialized Subjects: Specialized Subjects for TVL* got the lowest mean ($M=2.98$, $SD=.948$), which can be verbally interpreted as Oftentimes and qualitatively described as *To Some Extent*. This means that the Specialized Subjects for TVL has an average relevancy to the SHS curriculum to current endeavors, oftentimes, not necessary. The Philippine educational system encompasses both formal and non-formal education. Due to family tradition and cultural considerations, formal education is preferred to a non-formal system because society is degree-conscious. While there are attractive career opportunities for degree holders, technical education graduates have more employability prospects. Most people are prejudiced with regard to TVL, seeing it as second-class education. In reality, competency or skills training is an assurance of employability [30].

On the average, the variable, *Specialized Subjects* ($M=3.26$, $SD=0.81$), is verbally interpreted as *Always* and qualitatively described as *To a Very high/much extent*. This means that the

specialized subjects in all four subjects has great relevancy to the SHS curriculum to current students endeavors.

On the general average, the SHS Curriculum (Performance Standards) to Current Endeavor ($M=3.52$, $SD=0.68$), is verbally interpreted as *Always* and quantitatively described as *To a Very*

High/Much Extent. This finding indicates that this SHS Curriculum's performance standard significantly align with the current endeavors suggesting a strong correlation between what is taught and what is practice, fostering a high level of competence and proficiency among learners.

Table 6: Significant Difference of the Attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values when grouped according to course.

Profile	Variables	F	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Course	Christ-centeredness (Conscious)	0.611	1	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Charism (Creative)	1.09	0	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Charity (Compassion)	1.198	0	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Community (Collaboration)	0.757	1	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant
	Commission (Competence)	0.702	1	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant

Table 6 displays the results of statistical tests that evaluate the significant difference in the attainment of Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes or Paulinian Core Values, categorized according to courses. The table includes variables such as Christ-centeredness, Charism, Charity, Community, and Commission, along with their corresponding f-test and p-values. These statistical measures are used in hypothesis testing to determine the significance of differences among courses, reflecting the value characteristics this educational institution aims to instill in its students.

The table has four columns: F-test, P-value, Decision, and Interpretation. Each row represents the results regarding how Paulinians achieve these core values and assesses if there are statistically significant differences between courses in terms of the measured variables. The Decision column indicates whether the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected or not for each variable and course profile. In this table, for all variables, the null hypothesis is not rejected, suggesting that the course profile has no significant impact on the attainment of these core values among Paulinians. This implies a consistent manifestation of these values across different profiles or academic courses. Further examination of the data reveals that the variable with the highest F-test is "Charity (Compassion)," with an F-test of 1.19, indicating it as the most attainable core value among the courses. This is followed by Charism (Creative), with an F-test of 1.09. Conversely, the variable "Christ-centeredness (Competence)" exhibits the lowest f-test ($F=0.61$), alongside Community (Collaboration) at 0.75 and Commission (Competence) at 0.70. The value of Christ-centeredness also has the highest p-value of 0.872, while Charity (Compassion) has the lowest p-value.

Thus, the more reliable the generated scale, the higher the score [31]. Paulinians who exhibit collaboration and teamwork are accountable family members and citizens, focused on community building, and advocating for people, justice, peace, and environmental protection [32,33]. Reviews of these methods show overall positive student attitudes toward how they enhance class enjoyment and facilitate learning [34-36]. This analysis

emphasizes the consistent manifestation of core values across various courses, highlighting the institution's success in fostering these values among its students. Additionally, it prompts further exploration into the factors influencing the attainment of specific core values within the institution.

Conclusions

Based from the findings of the study, the following conclusions are offered:

The extent of attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values, significance of the most essential learning competencies in SHS and the relevance of the SHS curriculum (performance standards) to current endeavor is very high among the graduates of the Senior High School SY 2021-2022. It proves that the outcomes, competencies and standards provided by the institution clearly demonstrate and apply in the Higher Education, Work, and Business. Furthermore, the chosen course doesn't matter in terms of the attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes/Paulinian Core Values.

Recommendations

Based from the findings and significance of the study, the following recommendations were suggested:

- School Administrators may continue the best practices on curriculum implementation of the school in terms of standards, outcomes, and competencies. Further, the reasons to discontinue enrolling in St. Paul University Surigao may serve as a baseline to improve the services offered by the school.
- Teachers may use the data gathered to strengthen the weakest points, particularly on the extent of relevance of the specialized subjects of the TVL. Moreover, they can provide activities or avenue that would entice the graduates of the Senior High School to continue their higher education in the same institution.
- Future researchers may conduct tracer studies on other school years where pandemic struck and started. In

addition, they may correlate the extent of the attainment of the Paulinian Life Performance Outcomes to their chosen course.

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